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Patch Antenna Design for Sub-6 GHz 5G Radio

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"Tú llegaste al mundo para ser feliz/ You came into this world to be happy"
- Natalia Lafourcade

Abstract

The development of cost effective, low-profile antennas is vital for meeting the increased global demand on 5G and its ability to advance the world of wireless communications. The need for low-latency and high-speed to wide network areas is made possible through the implementation of effective antennas within our cities. The objective of this work was to design, simulate, and perform analysis of a probe-fed rectangular microstrip patch antenna for 5G radio applications, operating at a frequency of 3.5 GHz— in line with frequency bands currently allocated to UK network companies.

Preliminary literature review provided a foundation of knowledge on the various aspects of antenna design that were vital for the success of the project; this includes in depth understanding on the methods of antenna design, equations to consider, and the parameters that determine effective functionality. Using this knowledge, an initial patch antenna was designed via dimensions generated from a custom-made MATLAB script that utilized fundamental antenna equations to calculate the theoretical patch, substrate and ground size based on substrate permittivity and thickness, and the selected operating frequency proposed in this project. The antennas were designed and analysed using ANSYS HFSS, with parametric sweeps conducted on the theoretical antenna on the patch length, and feed location to determine optimal construction in terms of impedance matching and resonance.

Results for the theoretical, optimised, and a linear array of antenna are presented. With a centre frequency of 3.505 GHz, mounted on cost-effective FR-4 substrate with a permittivity (ϵ_r) of 4.4, the proposed optimised single element antenna demonstrated effective performance with excellent impedance matching, a reflection coefficient (S_{11}) of -35.303 dB at 3.5 GHz, an impedance bandwidth of 103.9 MHz ranging from 3.413–3.5552 GHz at a reflection coefficient of -10 dB, a gain of 3.72 dB, and directivity of 6.15 dB. To further enhance performance, a 1×4 linear array of antennas was designed and simulated, exhibiting a significant enhancement of gain and directivity of 20.26 dB and 22.68 dB respectively.

These findings indicate that the proposed antenna and the array configuration designed using MATLAB and ANSYS HFSS are applicable for operation in the Sub-6 GHz band of 5G radio, sufficient performance using FR-4 substrate allowed for cost-effective and miniaturised antenna design. The scope of the project was limited to simulated analysis alone.

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Nomenclature

Γ	Reflection Coefficient
ΔL	Length Extension due to Fringing Effects
ΔS	Magnitude of Change of S-Parameters Between 2 Consecutive Passes
ϵ_r	Relative Permittivity of Substrate
$\epsilon_{r_{eff}}$	Effective Permittivity
λ	Wavelength
Ω	Ohms
c	Speed of Light
D	Diameter of Dielectric of Coaxial
d	Diameter of Coaxial Probe
h	Thickness of Substrate
L	Length of Patch
L_S	Length of Substrate
W	Width of Patch
W_S	Width of Substrate
Z_L	Antenna Input Impedance
Z_o	Characteristic Impedance of Transmission Line
3D	Three-Dimensional
5G	Fifth Generation
DGS	Defective Ground Structure
dB	Decibels
EM	Electromagnetic
FR-4	Flame Retardant Type 4
GHz	Giga Hertz ($\times 10^9$ Hz)
HFSS	High-Frequency Structure Simulator
InnerC	Radius of the Inner Pin of Coaxial Cable
IoT	Internet of Things
MATLAB	Matrix Laboratory
MHz	Mega Hertz ($\times 10^6$ Hz)
mm	Millimetre ($\times 10^{-3}$ metres)
mmWave	Millimeter Wave
MSPA	Microstrip Patch Antenna
NR	New Radio
OuterC	Radius of Coaxial Dielectric
pec	Perfect Electric Conductor
PIFA	Planar Inverted-F Antenna
PML	Perfectly Matched Layer
Rogers RT/duroid 5880	Rogers Reinforced Teflon 5880
S-Parameters	Scattering Parameters
S_{11}	1 Port Network Reflection Coefficient
SMA	SubMiniature version A
Sub-6 GHz	Below 6 Giga Hertz
UE	User Equipment
VNA	Vector Network Analyser
VSWR	Voltage Standing Wave Ratio

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1 Introduction

In wireless communications, antennas are fundamental components that bridge the gap between a guided device such as a coaxial line, and free space. Antennas act as transducers, converting electrical signals from a transmitter into electromagnetic (EM) waves for propagation in free space, and then reversed back to electrical signals at a receiver. Antennas allow for the matching of impedance, 50Ω , from the transmission line to the free space impedance of 377Ω [1],[2].

There are various types of antennas that are suited for a broad range of applications, for example, horn antennas: These are simple antennas with a flared waveguide that carries the signal— this flared waveguide allows for better directivity and facilitates smooth impedance matching to free space [3]; however due to their size they are not suited for some applications such as 5G radio. The rapid development of 5G has accelerated demand of effective antenna design to meet the expectations of high data speeds and low-latency for a variety of applications such as the Internet of Things (IoT)[4].

Currently, 5G operation is allocated to two frequency bands, FR1 and FR2 also referred to as Sub-6 GHz and mmWave bands. FR1 ranging from 410 MHz to 7.125 GHz allows broad coverage due to its ability to overcome obstacles and is where the majority of the UK networks are allocated for 5G, and FR2, 24.25 GHz to 52.6 GHz, is utilised for short-range yet high-data rate transmission [5]. A centre frequency of 3.5 GHz has been defined in this project, it falls within the 3.4 – 3.8 GHz band defined by Ofcom as a focus for 5G, with major network companies such as O2, Vodafone and EE having allocations in this band [6]. Wireless communication in compact user equipment (UE) such as mobile phones brings demand for antennas that exhibit properties necessary for 5G implementation such as low-profile and high-gain patch antennas and planar inverted F antennas (PIFA) are examples of miniaturised and simple antennas suited for 5G implementation, with the ability to adjust parameters such as patch shape to meet the required gain and bandwidth demands[5], [7]. This report presents the design, simulation, and parametric optimisation of a patch antenna for Sub-6 GHz 5G radio operation at 3.5 GHz using MATLAB and ANSYS HFSS.

2 Aims and Objectives

The primary aim of the project was to design, simulate, and analyse a low-cost, compact probe fed rectangular patch antenna that exhibits high-performance within the Sub-6 GHz frequency band of 5G NR, centred on a frequency of 3.5 GHz. Primary focus was on the understanding of the factors and theoretical dimensions involved in the initial design for patch antennas, and the subsequent parameters that can be varied to optimise performance for 5G operation. The implementation of antenna arrays for simulated performance enhancement

was another aim.

In order to achieve these aims, the following objectives were established for this project, including:

- Utilisation of MATLAB script to derive initial theoretical dimensions for a rectangular patch antenna using fundamental equations.
- Design and simulate the theoretically derived antenna on electromagnetic (EM) simulation software such as ANSYS HFSS for primary analysis.
- Variation of antenna parameters such as probe location and patch length within HFSS using setup sweeps to optimise impedance matching and resonant frequency.
- Analyse results that determine the patch antenna's performance such as reflection coefficient, VSWR, gain, realised gain, and directivity to determine feasibility for Sub-6 GHz 5G NR operation.
- Design, simulation and comparison a 1×4 linear antenna array to that of the single element antenna.

Time limitations made this project constrained to simulated analysis using EM simulation software, ANSYS HFSS.

3 Literature Review

Extensive literature review was conducted for initial understanding of the basics of patch antenna design, the parameters that can be varied for enhanced performance, the implementation of arrays and the analysis of simulated and measured antennas. Literature also highlights the parameters that should be simulated for analysis and verification of utilisation in 5G radio.

3.1 Patch Antennas

Literature underlined the benefits of patch antenna design for 5G radio, their ability to provide a simplistic and low-cost design with adequate gain and directivity. The methodology in existing literature allowed for understanding of parameters derived for patch antenna development, and validated the equations utilised for this paper's antenna.

The benefits of patch antennas for 5G radio such as their compact size, low cost and ease of construction are discussed in [8] and highlights that their implementation for Sub-6 GHz applications can also have limitations such as small gain and bandwidth. Utilising fundamental equations for patch antenna design, a FR-4 mounted wideband patch antenna was proposed with operation in 3 frequency bands ($S_{11} < -10$ dB) of 1.2 GHz, 2.4 GHz and 5.6 GHz. The

simulated maximum gain and directivity of the antenna being 6.2355 dB and 7.386 dB respectively. This report also shows that there can be discrepancies between simulated and real-world results and that simulated analysis using EM software alone does not account for errors that can occur in real-world fabrication: The discrepancies in reflection coefficient results in the report are attributed to losses in the antenna's connector and substrate. The antenna design integrates performance enhancing techniques such as defective ground structure (DGS) where slots are etched in the ground plane of the antenna, as well as a reflective plate utilisation.

Figure 1: S_{11} Results Showing Multi-Band Operation of Patch Antenna [8]

A patch antenna for dual-band operation for both Sub-6 GHz and mmWave 5G application was proposed by [9] shows versatility in patch antenna design- the antenna was developed using a H-slot DGS, with tempered corners and parasitic strips added to each of the corners of the patch for enhanced impedance bandwidth and effective operation in both frequency bands which was achieved with resonant frequencies of 3.675 GHz in Sub-6 GHz band and 28.029 GHz for mmWave band. The S_{11} for these centre frequencies were -24.34 dB and -23.91 dB, a bandwidth of 60 MHz for Sub-6 GHz band and 670 MHz for the mmWave band. A limitation of the design is the complex design, and the challenges of fabrication without causing discrepancies between simulated and measured results.

Methods of varying patch size and shape are demonstrated in [10] where a rectangular microstrip line fed patch antenna mounted on FR-4 substrate with a Y-shaped and two rectangular-shaped slots etched in the patch, as well as 2 rectangular notches cut out of the patch was proposed. An operating frequency of 3.5 GHz was selected due to this band being of greatest focus for Sub-6 GHz 5G, an initial comparison of a conventional rectangular patch antenna to the proposed antenna was made and determined that the introduction of slots and notches enhanced bandwidth and S_{11} results and allowed for a resonant frequency at exactly 3.5 GHz. After design of the proposed antenna, it was validated with an equivalent circuit model, simulation using EM software, and real-world measurements using a vector

network analyser (VNA), with a there being a comparison of the theoretical, simulated and measured results. The proposed antenna's S_{11} results were -23.62 (simulated), -21.5 (theoretical), and -21.61 dB (measured) for a centre frequency of 3.5, 3.58, and 3.48 GHz, the measured impedance bandwidths were 530 MHz, 720 MHz, and 480 MHz respectively, and gains of 3.39 dB (simulated) and 3.2 dB (measured). The differences in results between the simulated and measured results are determined to be due to mismatches caused by the soldering of the SMA connector and feedline, and defects during the etching process.

Figure 2: Patch Antenna with Slots antenna's simulated [10]

This section provided validation that the use of FR-4 can provide adequate performance for patch antennas, and that the use of patch antennas allows for low-profile and moderate gain for Sub-6 GHz 5G radio, however the use of performance enhancing techniques and the discrepancies that can arise between simulated and measured results should be noted during the design process.

3.2 Array of Antennas

An array of antennas proposed in literature contribute to the understanding of how their implementation can enhance performance within this project. Antenna arrays contribute to increase in gain and directivity compared to single unit patch antenna with increasing the number of radiating elements allowing for better performance in Sub-6 GHz 5G applications.

The design of a 1×4 linear patch antenna array that is corporate fed for equal power distribution between the elements for a centre frequency of 3.5 GHz was proposed in [11]. The array was mounted on FR-4 substrate with a thickness of 3.2 mm and each element was spaced $\lambda/2$ apart in order to prevent mutual coupling of the array whilst still maintaining constructive interference where the radiated waves from the antenna elements align phases. The antenna has a single element size of 25 mm \times 30 mm, and the array has dimensions of 210 mm \times 30 mm. The single element antenna exhibited an S_{11} of -15 dB at a frequency of 3.47 GHz, gain of 4.63 dB, directivity of 4.62 dB, and has a bandwidth of 200 MHz. The linear array enhanced all measurements with an S_{11} of -30.28 dB at 3.48 GHz, gain of 5.53 dB, directivity of 5.93 dB, and bandwidth of 430 MHz. This highlights the improved operation that array implementation brings for 5G radio.

Figure 3: 1×4 Antenna Array [11]

A patch antenna with an H-shaped slot etched on the patch for bandwidth enhancement is presented in [12]: Its 2×4 array exhibited enhanced gain with the increase of elements from 6.54 dB to 14.89 dB. The antenna has a proposed centre frequency of 3.5 GHz with a simulated operational frequency range of 3.44–3.63 GHz, and a comparison of simulated and measured results was done, however the exact values for the measured parameters were not provided, graphical representation showed bandwidth for the measured results were visibly wider than the simulated results.

Figure 4: Fabricated 2×4 H-Slot Patch Antenna Array [12]

3.3 Changing Substrate Choice

The selection of a substrate for patch antennas is a trade-off between cost, antenna size (permittivity dependent), and performance [13].

The analysis of antenna performance in the mmWave band of 5G (28 GHz and 39 GHz) with varying substrates from Rogers RT/duroid 5880 ($\epsilon_r = 2.2$), Teflon ($\epsilon_r = 2.0$) and FR-4 ($\epsilon_r = 4.6$) with the same substrate thickness of 0.5 mm was proposed in [14]. Performance was analysed and determined that for both bands being considered, all substrates considered can provide resonance for 5G, with S_{11} being under -10 dB.

Table 1: S_{11} Comparison for Varying Substrates for 28 GHz and 39 GHz [14]

Substrate	28 GHz	39 GHz
FR-4	-46.47 dB	-22.4 dB
Rogers RT/duroid 5880	-25.8 dB	-21.9 dB
Teflon	-34.1 dB	-21.6 dB

For a frequency of 28 GHz, Rogers RT/duroid 5880 demonstrated the optimal performance with a gain of 6.71 dB, 75% radiation efficiency, and directivity of 7.96 dB, compared to that of 3.08 dB, 39.3%, and 7.13 dB for FR-4, and 6.51 dB, 71%, and 7.98 dB for Teflon. For the target frequency of 39 GHz, both Rogers RT/duroid 5880 and Teflon perform similarly with Teflon providing higher gain at 7.04 dB compared to 6.52 dB for Rogers RT/duroid 5880 and 2.76 dB for FR-4, and efficiency of 75% versus 69% for Rogers RT/duroid 5880 and 33.5% for FR-4. Rogers RT/duroid 5880 provided an interim patch size compared to Teflon and FR-4 with sizes of 3.29 mm×4.24 mm, 3.44 mm×4.37 mm, and 2.29 mm×3.2 mm respectively; only overall performance was considered for determining the optimal substrate, however for the antenna proposed in this report substrate choice was selected based on a trade-off on availability, cost, antenna patch size, and its ability to provide adequate performance for Sub-6 GHz 5G as opposed to the mmWave band.

Analysis of various substrates for rectangular and circular MSPAs for the Sub-6 GHz band of 5G in [15] indicated how lowering substrate permittivity increases the antenna's patch size but exhibits better reflection coefficient intensity, and higher gain and higher directivity. For the rectangular and circular patch antennas proposed, Alumina (ϵ_r 9.9) had the smallest patch size of 11.08 mm × 7.8 mm and radius of 5.44 mm respectively compared to dimensions of 20.77 mm × 16.98 mm and radius 10.16 mm for Teflon (ϵ_r 2.1). In terms of performance, at a centre frequency of 5.8 GHz, lower permittivity substrates, Teflon and Rogers RT/duroid 5880 exhibited the highest gain and directivity for the circular and rectangular patches at 4.12 dB gain, 5.74 dB directivity for a circular patch mounted on Teflon, and 4.24 dB gain, 5.84 dB directivity for a rectangular patch mounted on RT 5880. Teflon also exhibited the lowest reflection coefficient (S_{11}) of -44.2 dB for the rectangular patch and -42.96 dB for the circular patch; however, for the proposed center frequency of 5.8 GHz a circular patch antenna mounted on Teflon exhibited a reflection coefficient greater than -10 dB, making it inefficient for performance at this frequency.

Although FR-4 provided the lowest gain and efficiency in comparison to other substrates such as Rogers RT/duroid 5880 due to its higher loss tangent of 0.02, it is sufficient for 5G radio and is a cost effective choice for antenna design.

4 Antenna Design Methodology

Initial literature review allowed for the understanding of the core concepts behind antenna design, and the variables that need to be considered for effective functionality. In this section, the antenna design is addressed from the derivation of theoretical antenna parameters, design of the theoretical antenna using ANSYS HFSS, the modifications on patch length and feed location for proposed enhanced performance, design and simulation setup for the optimised antenna, and the design and simulation of a 1×4 array using the optimised antenna as the repeating element.

4.1 Predetermined Design Parameters

Design parameters were selected with regards to material cost, availability, and effectiveness, with selection validated by literature review of existing antenna designs and fundamental literature on antennas. The proposed patch antenna was designed to operate at a frequency of 3.5 GHz mounted on FR-4 substrate that has a permittivity ϵ_r of 4.4 and a thickness of 1 mm, this was selected due to its low cost and ability to provide a low-profile antenna [16]. There are many methods of feeding a patch antenna, such as microstrip line feed, coaxial probe, and aperture and proximity coupling, the antennas proposed in this project were fed via an SMA coaxial cable due to their enhanced impedance matching ability and their ability to provide wider bandwidth compared to microstrip feeding, however their design via EM simulation software is more difficult compared to microstrip implementation [1], [17]. The SMA coaxial cable simulated has a pin radius of 0.45 mm and dielectric radius of 1.5 mm, to ensure these dimensions for the simulated SMA coaxial cable were suited for an impedance of 50Ω , the relative permittivity of the coaxial's dielectric material, Teflon ($\epsilon_r = 2.1$), and the proposed dimensions were used to calculate impedance.

$$Z_0 = \frac{138 \cdot \log_{10} \left(\frac{D}{d} \right)}{\sqrt{\epsilon_r}} \quad (1)$$

Where Z_0 is the impedance of 50Ω , D is the coaxial cable outer diameter, d is the coaxial cable centre pin diameter, and ϵ_r is the permittivity of the coaxial cable dielectric material. The dimensions proposed provide the impedance of 50Ω that is set as a standard due to its compromises on loss, power, and voltage [18].

4.2 MATLAB Theoretical Dimensions Calculations

A custom MATLAB script was developed for the calculation of theoretical dimensions for an initial rectangular patch antenna as seen in Appendix A; the script consisted of the fundamental equations sourced through extensive literature review regarding patch antenna con-

struction such as equations Equations (1)–(7) outlined by Balanis in [1]. User defined inputs for the selected substrate's permittivity and thickness, as well as the established resonant frequency allowed the MATLAB script to determine the antenna dimensions. The patch width W was calculated using:

$$W = \frac{c}{2f_r} \sqrt{\frac{2}{\epsilon_r + 1}} \quad (2)$$

Where c is the speed of light, 299792458 m/s, f_r is the defined resonant frequency of 3.5 GHz, and ϵ_r is the FR-4 substrate permittivity of 4.4. To account for fringing effects which makes the antenna appear bigger than its physical size, an effective permittivity ϵ_r was calculated to derive the physical size of the antenna:

$$\epsilon_{r_{eff}} = \frac{\epsilon_r + 1}{2} + \frac{\epsilon_r - 1}{2} \left(1 + \frac{12h}{W}\right)^{-1/2} \quad (3)$$

Where h is the thickness of the FR-4 substrate in mm. The extended incremental length extension ΔL , is the length the patch is extended by due to fringing effects and was calculated by:

$$\Delta L = 0.412h \cdot \frac{(\epsilon_{r_{eff}} + 0.3) \left(\frac{W}{h} + 0.264\right)}{(\epsilon_{r_{eff}} - 0.258) \left(\frac{W}{h} + 0.8\right)} \quad (4)$$

The actual patch length, L , accounting for the length extension from fringing effects:

$$L = \frac{c}{2f_r \sqrt{\epsilon_{r_{eff}}}} - 2\Delta L \quad (5)$$

The substrate and ground plane width and length, W_s , and L_s , are given by:

$$W_s = 6h + W \quad (6)$$

$$L_s = 6h + L \quad (7)$$

Running the MATLAB script provided the theoretical dimensions for a rectangular patch antenna shown in Table 2, these values would be what is calculated using literature for a rectangular patch antenna with a proposed frequency of 3.5 GHz using a substrate with thickness of 1 mm and permittivity of 4.4, and were implemented in electromagnetic simulation software for an initial theoretical antenna design. Note that the SMA feed location was initially selected arbitrarily.

Table 2: Theoretical Patch Antenna Dimensions

Parameter	Value
Resonant Frequency, f_r	3.5 GHz
Substrate Relative Permittivity, ϵ_r	4.4
Substrate Thickness, h	1 mm
Patch Width, W	26.064 mm
Patch Length, L	20.209 mm
Effective Relative Permittivity, $\epsilon_{r_{eff}}$	4.107
Substrate Width, W_s	32.064 mm
Substrate Length, L_s	26.209 mm
SMA Pin Radius, $InnerC$	0.45 mm
SMA Dielectric Radius, $OuterC$	1.5 mm
SMA Feed Location, X_c, Y_c	(0 mm, -4 mm)

4.3 Single Patch Antenna

The antenna was designed using the student version ANSYS Electronics Desktop 2025 R2 with a modal solution type, and the user and MATLAB derived variables from Table 2 were defined in the design properties of the HFSS workspace. The antenna's substrate was designed using a box with FR-4 material with the permittivity of 4.4 and dimensions of 32.064 mm \times 26.209 mm \times 1 mm, centred on the workspace. The ground plane was designed to the base of the substrate with the same width and length as the substrate of 32.064 mm and 26.209 mm respectively but using a plane with no defined thickness. The antenna patch was designed as a plane with dimensions of 26.064 mm \times 20.209 mm and centred on top of the substrate. Both the ground plane and the patch were defined as perfect electric conductor (pec) surfaces.

Figure 5: Substrate and Patch Design on ANSYS HFSS.

For the antenna's feed, the centre pin of the SMA coaxial cable was defined as a cylinder with a radius of 0.45 mm and length of the coaxial height and substrate thickness, 6 mm, positioned 4 mm from the centre of the patch and fed below the patch, through the substrate and ground. The pin material of pec (perfect electric conductor) was selected. The dielectric of the coaxial cable encloses the centre pin, with a radius of 1.5 mm and a height of 5 mm, made from Teflon ($\epsilon_r = 2.1$). The dielectric touches the substrate but does not go through it and the outer face of the dielectric was assigned a boundary of a perfect conductor. To allow the coaxial centre pin to reach the patch, it was subtracted from the ground, substrate and patch, and the dielectric subtracted from the ground plane to allow it to reach the base of the substrate. A wave port excitation that provides the S-Parameters for analysis was defined for the bottom face of the dielectric with an integration line from the edge of the coaxial centre pin to the edge of the dielectric [19]. The wave port was normalised to the input impedance of 50Ω .

The simulation space was defined using a PML (perfectly matched layer) radiation boundary condition, this was selected as opposed to the standard radiating boundary due to its ability to absorb all EM fields infringing on the boundary regardless of the incident angle [20].

Figure 6: Antenna Design PML Boundary.

4.3.1 Solution Setup

A solution setup for a centre frequency of 3.5 GHz was established for analysis, with 14 cycles of mesh refinements and a maximum ΔS of 0.02 in order to have sufficient solution accuracy. A frequency sweep from 2.5 GHz to 4.5 GHz with 401 data points was set to provide a ± 1 GHz range around the 3.5 GHz centre frequency, and the design was validated for simulation.

Figure 7: Solution Setup.

Figure 8: Frequency Sweeps.

4.4 Parametric Studies

After analysis of the theoretical patch antenna using MATLAB derived dimensions, a series of parametric sweeps of the patch length and feed location of the coaxial cable were conducted for performance optimisation for a centre frequency of 3.5 GHz.

4.4.1 Ground and Substrate Dimensions

The ground and substrate dimensions were modified to dimensions of 35 mm for both width and length in the interest of design simplicity, this dimension was selected to ensure the dimensions were greater than that of the theoretical ground and substrate dimensions. This change of dimensions did have a slight change to S_{11} from the theoretical antenna. (see Appendix B)

4.4.2 Coaxial Feed Location

The position of the coaxial feed has an impact on the impedance matching between the feed and the antenna; good impedance matching is vital for ensuring reflection coefficients are low, minimising signal reflection back to the source [7].

On ANSYS HFSS, a parametric sweep of the coaxial feed's y location was established, ranging from -6 mm to -2 mm in steps of 0.5 mm and the reflection coefficient results were simulated for analysis of the optimal y location.

Figure 9: Setup of Sweep on Probe y Location.

The selection of y location was based on the lowest simulated S_{11} value which was at a location of -5.5 mm from the centre of the patch.

Figure 10: S_{11} Results of Theoretical Antenna with Changing Probe y Location From -6 mm to -2 mm in steps of 0.5 mm.

4.4.3 Patch Length

As established by the fundamental equations involved in the design of patch antennas, the resonance frequency of a patch antenna is influenced by its patch length [1]. After determining the optimal feed location and redefining this parameter in the ANSYS design properties, a parametric sweep on patch length was conducted from 18 mm to 22 mm in steps of 0.2 mm. The S_{11} results simulated were analysed in order to select the patch length where the minimum S_{11} was at a frequency closest to the target frequency of 3.5 GHz.

Figure 11: Sweep Setup for Patch Length Variation.

A patch length of 19.6 mm provided a minimum S_{11} at a frequency closest to 3.5 GHz (3.505 GHz) and was subsequently selected for the design of the optimised antenna.

Figure 12: S_{11} Results for Changing Patch Length with a Probe y Location of -5.5 mm.

4.5 Design of the Optimised Antenna

After determining the values for probe y location and patch length for the optimised antenna, they were redefined in the ANSYS HFSS design properties of the theoretical antenna's workspace and the antenna adjusted the parameters automatically. All materials and parameters not specified in the methodology for optimisation remained the same as the theoretical antenna.

Figure 13: Optimised Antenna Design on ANSYS HFSS.

4.6 Array Design

An antenna array is comprised of multiple radiating elements of which the inputs are combined [21]. After the optimised patch antenna was designed and analysed, focus shifted to the implementation of a 1×4 linear array using this optimised antenna via ANSYS HFSS parametric array setup. The distance between adjacent elements in the array was $\lambda/2$ to prevent sidelobes which are lobes of radiation in a direction other than the main beam, and avoid mutual coupling which is when the radiated waves from the elements get absorbed by one another resulting in degradation of signal performance in terms of gain, radiation pattern and coverage [22], [23], [21].

Figure 14: Array of Antenna Setup.

The array's gain, realised gain, and directivity were simulated for analysis and comparison

to the single element antenna.

4.7 3D Representation

For enhanced representation of the antenna, the antenna design was rendered using 3D modelling software, Blender, to provide a 360° representation of the antenna and its materials such as the metallic patch and ground, and the FR-4 substrate seen in Figure 15.

Figure 15: Patch Antenna Generated on Blender

5 Numerical Results

This project intended to design a patch antenna with a resonant frequency of 3.5 GHz that exhibited sufficient results in terms of reflection coefficient, gain and directivity for 5G radio applications. ANSYS HFSS was used to design and simulate the antenna with parametric sweeps to design an optimised antenna for enhanced simulated results, the dimensions that were amended for the final design of the antenna are detailed in Table 3

Table 3: Amended Patch Antenna Dimensions

Parameter	Initial Value	Final Value
Patch Length, L	20.209 mm	19.6 mm
Substrate Width, W_s	32.064 mm	35 mm
Substrate Length, L_s	26.209 mm	35 mm
SMA Feed Location, X_c, Y_c	(0 mm, -4 mm)	(0 mm, -5.5 mm)

The performance of the documented antenna designs has been observed and compared. The analysis of S-Parameters, VSWR, gain and realised gain, directivity, and bandwidth, with discussion of why performance changed between subsequent antennas recorded.

5.1 S-Parameters

Scattering parameters allow for an understanding of how much of the antenna's RF signal is reflected back, transmitted through or transmitted between ports in a network [24]. For the proposed single port network, S_{11} , or the reflection coefficient in decibels, is a measure of the amount of the antenna's signal that is reflected back to it as opposed to being transmitted [25] the equations for the reflection coefficient and S_{11} are:

$$\Gamma = \frac{Z_L - Z_o}{Z_L + Z_o} \quad (8)$$

$$S_{11} = 20 \log_{10}(\Gamma) \quad (9)$$

Where Γ is the reflection coefficient, Z_L is the antenna input impedance, and Z_o is the characteristic impedance of the transmission line (coaxial cable) [1]. For analysis, the S_{11} value of the antenna was simulated and presented in Figure 16, with the minimum value (deepest peak) defining the resonant frequency of the antenna: For the theoretical antenna, this was a value of -16.57 dB at a frequency of 3.36 GHz, and the optimised antenna has an S_{11} of -35.66 dB at a frequency of 3.505 GHz.

An S_{11} value below -10 dB is the industry standard for effective operation with only 10% of the transmitted signal being reflected back: The reflection percentage is derived by [26], [27]:

$$\text{Reflected Power (\%)} = 100 \times \Gamma^2 \quad (10)$$

Although the theoretical antenna can operate sufficiently at 3.36 GHz as the S_{11} value was below the standard, at the proposed operation frequency of 3.5 GHz the S_{11} is -1.868 dB meaning that at this frequency 65% of its transmitted power was reflected back, rendering it inoperable at this frequency. The optimised antenna has a lower simulated S_{11} of -35.303 dB at the proposed frequency of 3.5 GHz with only 0.029% of the power being reflected back, meaning that the antenna operates effectively at the proposed centre frequency.

Figure 16: Simulated S_{11} plots of the patch antenna Theoretically Derived Antenna (a) and Proposed Optimised Antenna (b).

5.2 Impedance Bandwidth

The bandwidth of an antenna describes the range of frequencies in which the antenna operates within an acceptable value compared to that of the centre frequency [1]. This acceptable value varies depending on deployment, for example, some smartphone antennas will state a -6 dB impedance bandwidth [28]. A -10 dB impedance bandwidth was accounted for in this project, where 90% of the antenna's reflected power is accepted, Table 4 shows the -10 dB impedance bandwidths for the simulated antennas.

Table 4: -10 dB Reflectivity Bandwidth Comparison

Antenna	Bandwidth Range (GHz)	Bandwidth (MHz)
Theoretical	3.3330–3.3901	57.1
Optimised	3.4513–3.5552	103.9

The bandwidth increased by 46.8 MHz from the theoretical to optimised antenna; patch antennas are known for having narrow bandwidth due to their low-profile, the bandwidth of 103.9 MHz measured for the optimised antenna represents 2.9% of the centre frequency and is comparable to patch antenna's expected bandwidths of 2–5% of their centre frequency [1]. This optimised bandwidth value fell between values stated in literature; [9] had a lower bandwidth of 60 MHz for Sub-6 GHz 5G where as [10] had a greater bandwidth of 530 MHz for 3.5 GHz.

5.3 VSWR

Voltage standing wave ratio (VSWR) is another measure of how efficient the RF power is transmitted from with a 1.0 VSWR being deemed perfect impedance matching, similar to the reflection coefficient [29].

$$\text{VSWR} = \frac{1 + |\Gamma|}{1 - |\Gamma|} \quad (11)$$

The theoretical antenna has a minimum VSWR of 1.35 at 3.36 GHz; however, at a frequency of 3.5 GHz this rises to 9.38; in industry any VSWR below 2 ($-9.54 \text{ dB } S_{11}$) is deemed acceptable; therefore, the theoretical antenna is not effective for this frequency.

Figure 17: VSWR Plot for Theoretical Antenna (a) and Optimised Antenna (b).

The optimised antenna has a VSWR of 1.034 at 3.505 GHz which is a near perfect impedance matching.

5.4 Gain and Realised Gain

The gain of an antenna is a measure of the intensity of radiation in a given direction, compared to that of the intensity observed if the power accepted by the antenna were radiated isotropically (evenly in all directions), with realised gain taking into account ohmic and reflection coefficients, this realised gain typically is lower due to impedance losses [1], [21]. Table 5 shows the comparison of gain and realised gain between the theoretical, optimised and array antennas.

Table 5: Gain and Realised Gain Comparison

Antenna	Gain, dB	Realised Gain, dB
Theoretical	2.32	-2.24
Optimised	3.72	3.72
Array	20.26	20.25

The theoretical antenna achieved a gain of 2.32 dB, and a realised gain of -2.24 dB; this is low and indicative of poor impedance matching whereas the optimised antenna had an increased yet modest gain of 3.72 dB and realised gain of the same value of 3.72 dB which indicates that there are minimal to no losses from impedance mismatching. The gain of the optimised antenna is comparable to that of [10], which demonstrated a simulated gain of 3.39 dB for a frequency of 3.5 GHz.

Figure 18: 2D Gain Plots

The antenna array exhibited enhanced gain compared to the single element optimised antenna, with a gain of 20.26 dB and realised gain of 20.25 dB.

5.5 Directivity

The directivity of an antenna is the ratio of the radiation intensity in a given direction from the antenna to the radiation intensity averaged over all directions [21]. The 3D polar plots seen in Figure 19 shows the directivity red section of the node showing the region of highest concentration of the antenna's radiated power, indicating the highest directivity and gain [15].

Figure 19: 3D Directivity Plots

The linear array drastically enhanced directivity with a maximum value of 22.68 dB. The values simulated for directivity are comparable to literature, [11] had a single element directivity of 4.62 dB which increased to 5.93 dB when in an array configuration. In terms of the shape of the polar plots, it is evident that the optimised antenna has a more suppressed back lobe than the theoretical antenna indicating there is minimised energy focused in unwanted directions. The linear array has a narrower main beam which shows that the energy is being highly concentrated in a single direction, there are also side lobes present at $\pm 30^\circ$, $\pm 90^\circ$, $\pm 150^\circ$, and a back lobe at 180° .

6 Discussion of Results

The simulated results demonstrate that optimisation of the theoretical antenna provided enhancements of all measurable parameters. The reduction of patch length from 20.209 mm to 19.6 mm and a change of probe y location to -5.5 mm has allowed for the enhancement of S-Parameters, VSWR, gain and realised gain, and directivity. These enhancements

demonstrate that parametric optimisation is effective for patch antenna design.

The parametric sweep on patch length showed that decreasing the patch length of the antenna increased the operating frequency. The resonant frequency of an antenna is a function of its length, with there being an inverse relationship between frequency and patch length— as the patch length was decreased, resonant frequency increased, with a length of 19.6 mm providing an operating frequency shift closer to the proposed frequency of 3.5 GHz, with minimum reflection coefficient at 3.505 GHz compared to the 3.36 GHz for a patch length of 20.209 mm [1]. This indicates that the MATLAB derived calculations for the antenna were a good starting point for initial design, however the parameters required adjustments in order to account for fringing effects. Changing the ground and substrate dimensions to 35 mm×35 mm changed the resonant frequency slightly, but this was a small change and deemed not significant enough to affect the performance of the antenna. This change was a cosmetic change and allowed for simplicity of design.

The changing of y location for the SMA coaxial feed from -4 mm to -5.5 mm from the centre of the patch allowed for a reduction in impedance mismatching, meaning that the majority of the antenna's power was radiated rather than reflected [29]. An antenna's input impedance varies throughout the patch, with the centre having an impedance of 0Ω and this impedance increases towards the edges of the patch— the probe y location of -5.5 mm from the patch centre showed that this location was where input impedance most closely matched the feed impedance of 50Ω . This impedance matching allowed for the enhancement of the simulated parameters for S_{11} , gain, and bandwidth [7]. Improved impedance matching was first observed via the S_{11} results for the parametric sweep on probe location, as the probe location varied there was a noticeable change in S_{11} , with a location of -5.5 mm showing the deepest peak. S_{11} is a numerical measure of how well the antennas input impedance matches the feed impedance, with a more negative value of S_{11} correlating to better matching and more of the power being radiated rather than reflected [24]. The improvement of S_{11} due to impedance matching also resulted in the enhancement of bandwidth due to a wider range of frequencies having S_{11} below -10 dB. The VSWR of 1.0335 for the optimised antenna validated that the impedance matching was near perfect, as well as gain and realised gain being the same value of 3.72 dB which shows that there are negligible losses derived from impedance mismatching.

The implementation of a linear array of antennas using the optimised antenna as the repeating element allowed for an increase in directivity and gain, this is due to the radiation patterns of each array element superposing. The radiated energy of each element undergoes constructive interference, this enhances the power radiated in some directions, and destructive interference which results in nulls in the radiation pattern as seen as the side lobes in Figure 19. This combination of radio waves results in a concentration of power in a certain direction which is evident in the increase of gain between the optimised single element and the linear array

[30]. The $\lambda/2$ spacing between elements of the array allows for reduced mutual coupling and the increased directivity and gain [23].

7 Conclusion and Future Work

This work successfully completed the primary aims of derivation, design, and simulation of a theoretical antenna for a centre frequency of 3.5 GHz and the subsequent design of an optimised antenna that had modifications made to patch length, ground size, and feed location. Performance determining parameters such as the reflection coefficient, VSWR, gain, realised gain, and directivity were analysed and highlighted the effectiveness of modifying the theoretical antenna. The work verified that an antenna for the Sub-6 GHz band of 5G radio can be made in a simple manner, with varying parameters delivering enhanced performance for a wider bandwidth of 103.9 MHz that encapsulates the proposed centre frequency of 3.5 GHz.

The movement of the SMA cable's y location from -4 mm to -5.5 mm was the most vital parameter change as it allowed for enhanced impedance matching, which in turn allowed for an increase in gain, directivity, and S_{11} . The reduction in patch length to 19.6 mm provided a shift of resonant frequency close to the proposed frequency of 3.5 GHz. The implementation of linear arrays using the proposed single element provided further enhancements to the gain and directivity for Sub-6 GHz 5G radio compared to that of the single element antenna.

Due to time limitations, the project was constrained to simulation-based derivation of results for analysis using ANSYS HFSS. Real-world fabrication and measurements using a VNA would allow for validation that the proposed optimised antenna is functional for 5G radio; it was seen in [10] that discrepancies can arise between simulated and measured results which can modify its functionality such as soldering tolerances of the transmission line. With widespread implementation of 5G requiring large quantities of antennas, there is a demand for low-cost antennas; material choices such as the use of FR-4 for this project was done as a trade-off between cost and performance, literature showed that the selection of more costly substrates such as Rogers RT/duroid 5880 could provide enhanced performance [31],[14].

To further enhance antenna design for 5G radio, this project can be further extended for experimental evaluation as follows:

- Extension of this project from only simulation to manufacturing through the fabrication and measured analysis of the optimised antenna, with comparison of performance with simulated results to determine real-world feasibility of the antenna for Sub-6 GHz 5G.
- Design and simulation of an antenna with varying substrates for analysis performance at 3.5 GHz to determine optimal substrate for 3.5 GHz.
- Development using enhancement techniques such as DGS and slots etched in the patch to understand modifications that can be made for performance enhancement of MSPAs.

References

- [1] C. A. Balanis, *Antenna theory: analysis and design*. John Wiley & Sons.
- [2] L. Sevgi, “The antenna as a transducer: Simple circuit and electromagnetic models,” vol. 49, no. 6, pp. 211–218. [Online]. Available: <http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/4455907/>
- [3] O. L. Daniyan, F. E. Opara, B. I. Okere, N. Aliyu, N. Ezechi, J. Wali, J. Adejoh, K. Eze, J. Chapi, and C. Justus, “Horn antenna design: the concepts and considerations,” vol. 4, no. 5, pp. 706–708.
- [4] R. P. G. A, A. M, V. Jonathan A, S. Kumar M, and V. Priyan R, “Design and optimization of leaf-inspired antenna for enhanced sub-6 GHz 5g performance,” in *2025 3rd International Conference on Integrated Circuits and Communication Systems (ICICACS)*. IEEE, pp. 01–05. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10968106/>
- [5] W. Ahmad, A. Ali, and W. T. Khan, “Small form factor PIFA antenna design at 28 GHz for 5g applications,” in *2016 IEEE International Symposium on Antennas and Propagation (APSURSI)*, pp. 1747–1748.
- [6] D. Ramsay and J. Rogerson, “5g frequencies in the UK,” publication Title: <https://5g.co.uk>. [Online]. Available: <https://5g.co.uk/guides/5g-frequencies-in-the-uk-what-you-need-to-know/>
- [7] S. Sharma, C. C. Tripathi, and R. Rishi, “Impedance matching techniques for microstrip patch antenna,” vol. 10, no. 28, pp. 1–16.
- [8] H. J. R. R and H. S, “Micro-strip patch antenna for 5g sub 6 GHz applications,” in *2022 International Interdisciplinary Humanitarian Conference for Sustainability (IIHC)*. IEEE, pp. 616–620. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10060179/>
- [9] K. N. Hasan, P. Sutradhar, and S. Ahmed, “Integrated dual-band microstrip patch antenna for sub-6 GHz and mm-wave 5g communication,” in *2025 International Conference on Quantum Photonics, Artificial Intelligence, and Networking (QPAIN)*, pp. 1–6.
- [10] R. K. Verma, B. Priya, M. Singh, P. Singh, A. Yadav, and V. K. Singh, “Equivalent circuit model-based design and analysis of microstrip line fed electrically small patch antenna for sub-6 GHz 5g applications,” vol. 36, no. 17, p. e5595.

- [11] A. Jayaprakash, R. M. V, and A. J. S, “Design and analysis of compact array antenna for 5g and radar applications,” in *2025 Advanced Computing and Communication Technologies for High Performance Applications (ACCTHPA)*, pp. 1–5.
- [12] H. Huang, Y. Yu, M. Wu, and Q. Wang, “A h-shape antenna array for 5g sub-6ghz communication,” in *2023 IEEE 11th Asia-Pacific Conference on Antennas and Propagation (APCAP)*, vol. volume1, pp. 1–2.
- [13] M. A. Ahasan and M. Billah, “Design and performance analysis of compact microstrip patch antenna (MPA) for wireless fidelity communication,” vol. 72, no. 1, p. 256. [Online]. Available: <https://link.springer.com/10.1186/s44147-025-00837-z>
- [14] E. Vythee and R. A. Jugurnauth, “Microstrip patch antenna design and analysis with varying substrates for 5g,” in *2020 3rd International Conference on Emerging Trends in Electrical, Electronic and Communications Engineering (ELECOM)*, pp. 141–146.
- [15] F. Göksel and S. Karamzadeh, “Evaluating substrate influence on rectangular and circular microstrip patch antennas for 5g,” in *2024 IEEE Workshop on Microwave Theory and Technology in Wireless Communications (MTTW)*, pp. 96–101.
- [16] S. Chaimool, N. Prasert, and C. Raklua, “Low-cost FR-4 metasurface-enhanced microstrip patch antenna array for wideband 5g millimeter-wave applications,” in *2024 IEEE International Workshop on Antenna Technology (iWAT)*. IEEE, pp. 118–121. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10535796/>
- [17] S. Bello, “Design and performance comparison of coaxial probe and microstrip line feeding techniques in patch antennas.”
- [18] Z. Peterson, “The mysterious 50 ohm impedance: Where it came from and why we use it.” [Online]. Available: <https://resources.altium.com/p/mysterious-50-ohm-impedance-where-it-came-and-why-we-use-it>
- [19] ANSYS, “Module 6: HFSS lumped and wave port basics.”
- [20] Ansys. Radiation boundaries. [Online]. Available: https://ansyshelp.ansys.com/public/Views/Secured/Electronics/v251/en/Subsystems/HFSS/Content/HFSS/RadiationBoundaries.htm?tocpath=HFSS%20Help%7CHFSS%20Technical%20Notes%7CBoundaries%20Technical%20Notes%7C_____3
- [21] “IEEE standard for definitions of terms for antennas.” [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/6758443>
- [22] M. Rohaninezhad, M. J. Asdabadi, C. Ghobadi, and J. Nourinia, “Mutual coupling in the antennas,” p. 105.

- [23] H. Wang, D. G. Fang, Y. P. Xi, C. Z. Luan, and B. Wang, "On the mutual coupling of the finite microstrip antenna arrays," in *2007 International Symposium on Electromagnetic Compatibility*, pp. 10–14.
- [24] A. Theory. S parameters. [Online]. Available: <https://www.antenna-theory.com/definitions/sparameters.php>
- [25] Z. Peterson. S11 parameter vs. return loss vs. reflection coefficient: When are they the same? [Online]. Available: <https://resources.altium.com/p/s11-vs-return-loss-vs-reflection-coefficient-when-are-they-same>
- [26] S. F. Jilani, A. Rahimian, Y. Alfadhl, and A. Alomainy, "Low-profile flexible frequency-reconfigurable millimetre-wave antenna for 5g applications," vol. 3, no. 3, p. 035003.
- [27] Northeastrf. Return loss to mismatch calculator. [Online]. Available: <https://northeastrf.com/return-loss-calculator/>
- [28] Y. Wang, L. Sun, Z. Du, and Z. Zhang, "Antenna design for modern mobile phones: A review," vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 1–36, ISBN: 2836-9440.
- [29] G. Hardesty. VSWR: Impedance matching in antennas & antenna cables. [Online]. Available: <https://www.data-alliance.net/blog/vswr-impedance-matching-in-antennas?srsltid=AfmBOoqK54Vucqm4vD34GIQRiirk5jQiACt4D8N7i5LnYYUDDvnk6mmF>
- [30] M. Gal-Katziri, A. Fikes, and A. Hajimiri, "Flexible active antenna arrays," vol. 6, no. 1, p. 85.
- [31] J. Gieske. Types of 5g antennas: A guide to technologies for next-gen connectivity. [Online]. Available: <https://nybsys.com/types-of-5g-antennas/>

A MATLAB Script

The following MATLAB script calculates the patch antenna dimensions:

```

1 %MATLAB SCRIPT TO RUN CALCULATIONS FOR ANTENNA DESIGN
clear;
3 %Enter Known Variables
Er = input('Enter Substrate Permittivity ');
5 h = input('Enter Substrate Height/mm ');
f = input('Enter Resonant Frequency/GHz ');
7 c=299792458; %Speed of light
h=h*1e-3; %convert to m
9 f=f*1e9; %convert to Hz
%Calculations
11 WPatch=(c/(2*f))*(sqrt(2/(Er+1))); %Width of Patch
Eeff=((Er+1)/2)+(((Er-1)/2)*sqrt(1/(1+((12*h)/WPatch)))); %Effective
    Permittivity
13 Leff= (c/(2*f*sqrt(Eeff))); %Effective Length
dL= (((0.412*h)*(Eeff+0.3)*((WPatch/h)+0.264)))/((Eeff-0.258)*((WPatch/h)
    +0.8));
15 LPatch= Leff-(2*dL); %Length of Patch
WSubstrate= WPatch + (6*h); %Substrate and Ground Width
17 LSubstrate= LPatch + (6*h); %Substrate and Ground Length
%z= 90*((Er*Er)/(Er-1))*((LPatch/WPatch)^2);
19 lambda=c/f;
%Display Results
21 disp(['Patch Width=', num2str(WPatch*(1e3)), 'mm']);
disp(['Patch Length=', num2str(LPatch*(1e3)), 'mm']);
23 disp(['Substrate Width=', num2str(WSubstrate*(1e3)), 'mm']);
disp(['Substrate Length=', num2str(LSubstrate*(1e3)), 'mm']);
25 %disp(['Input Impedance=', num2str(z), 'Ohms']);
disp(['lambda =', num2str(lambda*(1e3)), 'mm']);

```

Code 1: MATLAB Antenna Design Script

B S_{11} Results Comparison: Theoretical Antenna vs Non-Optimised Antenna with Square Ground Plane

(a) Theoretical Antenna

(b) Theoretical Antenna with Ground Dimensions 35×35 mm

Figure 20: Simulated S_{11} plots of Theoretically Derived Antenna (a) and Theoretical Derived Antenna with a Square Ground Shape.